

**FOUR PERSPECTIVES ON SECONDARY TERMS IN THE
DAVENPORT-HEILBRONN THEOREMS**

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Abstract

This paper is an expanded version of the author's lecture at the Integers Conference 2011. We discuss the secondary terms in the Davenport-Heilbronn theorems on cubic fields and 3-torsion in class groups of quadratic fields. Such secondary terms had been conjectured by Datskovsky-Wright and Roberts, and proofs of these or closely related secondary terms were obtained independently by Bhargava, Shankar, and Tsimerman, Hough, Zhao, and Taniguchi and the author.

In this paper we discuss the history of the problem and highlight the diverse methods used in several papers to address it.

1. Introduction

This paper concerns the following two theorems.

Theorem 1. *Let $N_3^\pm(X)$ count the number of cubic fields K with $0 < \pm \text{Disc}(K) < X$. We have*

$$N_3^\pm(X) = C^\pm \frac{1}{12\zeta(3)} X + K^\pm \frac{4\zeta(1/3)}{5\Gamma(2/3)^3\zeta(5/3)} X^{5/6} + o(X^{5/6}), \quad (1)$$

where $C^- = 3$, $C^+ = 1$, $K^- = \sqrt{3}$, and $K^+ = 1$.

Theorem 2. *For any quadratic field with discriminant D , let $\text{Cl}_3(D)$ denote the 3-torsion subgroup of the ideal class group $\text{Cl}(\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{D}))$, we have*

$$\sum_{0 < \pm D < X} \#\text{Cl}_3(D) = \frac{3 + C^\pm}{\pi^2} X + K^\pm \frac{8\zeta(1/3)}{5\Gamma(2/3)^3} \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{p^{1/3} + 1}{p(p+1)}\right) X^{5/6} + o(X^{5/6}), \quad (2)$$

and where the sum ranges over fundamental discriminants D , the product is over all primes, and the constants are as before.

The main terms are due to Davenport and Heilbronn [15], and the secondary term in Theorem 1 was conjectured by Roberts [32] and implicitly by Datskovsky and Wright [14].

The secondary terms were expected to be difficult to prove. However, progress has recently made in four independent works, using a variety of methods. Both results above have been proved by Bhargava, Shankar, and Tsimerman [7], using the geometry of numbers, and by Taniguchi and the present author [37], using Shintani zeta functions. Hough [24] has proved a variation of Theorem 2 by studying the distribution of Heegner points in the complex upper half-plane, and Zhao [45] has obtained a variation of Theorem 1 for function fields, using algebraic geometry.¹

The author's lecture at the 2011 Integers Conference explained (briefly) how each of these four approaches sheds light on these secondary terms, and this paper is an expanded version of our lecture. We begin with some background on counting fields and on counting cubic fields in particular. The reader might skip to Section 4 for our discussion of the secondary terms.

2. Counting Fields in General

How does one count number fields? This question has been addressed in many excellent expository accounts, such as that by Cohen, Diaz y Diaz, and Olivier [10], or Chapter 6 of Bhargava's ICM proceedings article [5]. Therefore, our overview will be brief. To a large extent we concentrate on the "trivial" problem of counting quadratic fields, as some observations on this problem anticipate the methods developed to count cubic fields with good error terms.

Two early important theorems in the subject were proved by Minkowski and Hermite:

Theorem 3. (Hermite) *There are only finitely many number fields of bounded discriminant.*

Theorem 4. (Minkowski) *The discriminant of a number field K of degree n satisfies*

$$|\text{Disc}(K)| \geq \left(\frac{n^n}{n!}\right)^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)^n. \quad (3)$$

If we write $n = r + 2s$, where r is the number of real embeddings of K , and s is the number of pairs of complex embeddings, we may replace $(\pi/4)^n$ with $(\pi/4)^{2s}$. Moreover, by Stirling's formula $n! \sim \sqrt{2\pi n} \left(\frac{n}{e}\right)^n$ and therefore

$$|\text{Disc}(K)| \geq \left(e^2 \cdot \frac{\pi}{4} + o(1)\right)^n = \left(5.803 \cdots + o(1)\right)^n. \quad (4)$$

¹The error terms in [24] and [45] are larger than the secondary terms at present, but both of these approaches naturally *explain* the secondary term, and both authors are currently working on refining their methods.

The constant $\frac{e^2\pi}{4}$ can be improved; see Odlyzko [29]. Conversely, this bound is sharp apart from the constant; Golod and Shafarevich [21] proved the existence of an *infinite class field tower* of fields K for which $|\text{Disc}(K)|^{1/n}$ is constant.²

To prove these theorems³, use the r embeddings $K \hookrightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and the s pairs of embeddings $K \hookrightarrow \mathbb{C}$ to embed the ring of integers of K as a lattice in n -dimensional space. As proved by Minkowski, any convex body centered around the origin, whose volume is greater than $2^n|\text{Disc}(K)|^{1/2}$, must contain a lattice point other than zero. However, this point must have norm at least 1, and geometric considerations allow one to conclude Minkowski's lower bound.

Hermite's theorem can be proved in a similar way. We again use Minkowski's convex body theorem to find an element $\alpha \in \mathcal{O}_K$, the sizes of whose complex embeddings are all small, and which is guaranteed to generate K over \mathbb{Q} . The minimal polynomial of α is equal to $\prod_{\sigma}(X - \sigma(\alpha))$, where σ ranges over all real and complex embeddings of K , and the bounds obtained from Minkowski's theorem yield bounds on the coefficients of the minimal polynomial of α . For a fixed discriminant bound, there are only finitely many such polynomials, and thus only finitely many possibilities for K .

Remark. Although this proof of Hermite's theorem relies on Minkowski's work, Hermite's paper [23] preceded Minkowski's by over thirty years. Hermite claimed in [23] that there are finitely many fields of bounded discriminant *with fixed degree*; the stronger claim of Theorem 3 seems to depend also on Minkowski's work.

These proofs yield results about fields of each fixed degree, and so far this has been a natural way to count them. In what follows, let $N_n(X)$ be the number of fields K of degree n with $|\text{Disc}(K)| < X$. (Results are also known when the sign of the discriminant, or more generally the number of real embeddings, is specified.)

We have the following results (excluding $n = 3$):

$n = 1$. There is only \mathbb{Q} .

$n = 2$. We have the equality of Dirichlet series

$$\sum_{[K:\mathbb{Q}]=2} |\text{Disc}(K)|^{-s} = -1 + \left(1 - 2^{-s} + 2 \cdot 4^{-s}\right) \frac{\zeta(s)}{\zeta(2s)}, \tag{5}$$

and it follows that

$$N_2(X) = \frac{6}{\pi^2}X + O(\sqrt{X}). \tag{6}$$

The typical proof of (6) estimates, for each squarefree odd q , the number of integers n divisible by q^2 satisfying the 2-adic conditions implied by (6), and then

²Martinet [27] gave the example of $F = \mathbb{Q}(\zeta_{11} + \zeta_{11}^{-1}, \sqrt{-46})$, which he proved to have an infinite 2-class field tower, for which $|\text{Disc}(K)|^{1/n} = 92.2 \dots$ for each field K . We refer to Lemmermeyer [25] for a discussion of related issues, along with a very thorough bibliography.

³See [28], Ch. III.2 for complete proofs.

uses inclusion-exclusion to sieve for squarefreeness. The details are commonly left as an exercise for beginning analytic number theory students. However, it was not until the recent work of Belabas, Bhargava, and Pomerance [2] that the analogous method was developed to yield power-saving error terms for $N_3(X)$.

How does one estimate the number of integers n with $0 < n < X$ and $q^2|n$? (For simplicity of explanation, we ignore the 2-adic conditions.) This is a lattice-point counting problem in a one-dimensional vector space, so the answer is $\frac{1}{q^2}$ times the length of the interval $(0, X)$ plus an error of $O(1)$. This is trivial, but its generalization to the cubic case, where one counts $\text{GL}_2(\mathbb{Z})$ -orbits on a four-dimensional lattice, satisfying local conditions $(\text{mod } q^2)$ and a global condition $0 < \pm \text{Disc}(f) < X$, is not. (The higher dimensional analogues are still less so!)

These integers may also be counted using analytic number theory. By Perron’s formula, we have

$$\sum_{\substack{0 < n < X \\ q^2|n}} 1 = \int_{2-i\infty}^{2+i\infty} q^{-2s} \zeta(s) X^s \frac{ds}{s}, \tag{7}$$

and these sums may be estimated by shifting the contour and using the functional equation of the zeta function. This functional equation relies on Poisson summation, and so again relies on the question’s interpretation as a lattice point counting problem.

Even the most diehard fan of contour integration would likely prefer the trivial proof, but this analytic method also generalizes usefully to the cubic case, where the Riemann zeta function is replaced with a *Shintani zeta function*.

These two counting techniques, in combination with the inclusion-exclusion sieve, are the starting points of the geometric and analytic proofs of Theorems 1 and 2, respectively!

We note one additional point related to (5). Wright [42] observed that this Dirichlet series has the beautiful representation

$$\sum_{[K:\mathbb{Q}]=2} |\text{Disc}(K)|^{-s} = \prod_p \left(\frac{1}{2} \sum_{[K_v:\mathbb{Q}_p] \leq 2} |\text{Disc}(K_v)|_p^s \right), \tag{8}$$

and proved this in a much more general framework. (He obtained similar formulas for degree n cyclic extensions of any number field.) His results follow from considering a nontrivial ‘twist’ of the adelic zeta function of Tate’s thesis [39]. This twist makes the affine line into a *prehomogeneous vector space*, with the action ϕ of $\text{GL}(1)$ given by $\phi(t)x = t^n x$.

Essentially, a vector space is prehomogeneous if it has an action of an algebraic group G , which is transitive over \mathbb{C} apart from the vanishing locus of an irreducible polynomial. This ‘prehomogeneous’ property is essential both in Bhargava’s work and in the zeta function approach pioneered by Sato and Shintani [34]; cubic, quar-

tic, and quintic fields are parameterized by lattice points⁴ up to the action of $G(\mathbb{Z})$, and these may be counted geometrically or analytically.

Wright’s work on (8) and its generalizations mirrors his work with Datskovsky [41, 13, 14] on the Shintani zeta function associated to cubic fields, and this latter work is at the heart of the analytic approach to counting cubic fields. In follow-up work, Wright and Yukié [43] proposed a program to enumerate quartic and quintic fields by studying the zeta functions associated to appropriate prehomogeneous vector spaces. So far their program has not succeeded; however:

$n = 4, 5$. Bhargava [3, 6] proved the asymptotic formulas

$$N_4(X, S_4) \sim \frac{5}{24} \prod_p (1 + p^{-2} - p^{-3} - p^{-4}) \cdot X, \tag{9}$$

$$N_5(X) \sim \frac{13}{120} \prod_p (1 + p^{-2} - p^{-4} - p^{-5}) \cdot X. \tag{10}$$

The count $N_4(X, S_4)$ includes only quartic fields with Galois group S_4 , and (9) implies an asymptotic for $N_4(X)$ in combination with work of Baily [1], Cohen, Diaz y Diaz, and Olivier [9], and Wong [40]. Bhargava’s geometric approach may be considered an extension of the methods described in Sections 3 and 6.

$n > 5$. For $n > 5$, Bhargava conjectured [4] that $N_n(X, S_n) \sim C_n X$. The explicit constants C_n have natural interpretations as Euler products; each Euler factor represents the ‘probability’ that a field K of degree n has a certain localization. Ellenberg and Venkatesh [19] have proved the best upper bound to date; namely $N_n(X) \ll X^{\exp(C\sqrt{\log n})}$.

It is unclear whether prehomogeneous vector spaces may be used to obtain formulas for $N_n(X)$ for $n > 5$. By a classification theorem of Sato and Kimura [33], it is known that there are no reduced, irreducible, and reductive prehomogeneous vector spaces parameterizing rings of rank > 5 ; it remains to be seen whether there are any prehomogeneous vector spaces not satisfying these assumptions which parameterize such rings.

2.1. Counting Torsion Elements in Class Groups

The problem of counting 3-torsion elements in class groups of quadratic fields is related to that of counting cubic fields. If $D \neq 1$ is a fundamental discriminant, then class field theory provides a bijection between subgroups of $\text{Cl}(\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{D}))$ of index 3, and unramified cyclic cubic extensions of $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{D})$. Such extensions, in turn, correspond to (non-Galois) cubic extensions of \mathbb{Q} whose discriminant is D . Therefore, counting 3-torsion elements in quadratic fields is equivalent to counting cubic fields whose discriminant is fundamental, which are those not totally ramified at any prime.

⁴Not *all* of the $G(\mathbb{Z})$ -orbits correspond to fields, as we will see in the cubic case.

Therefore, this problem may be treated as a variation of the problem of counting cubic fields. This is the approach of Sections 3, 5, and 6; however, there are other approaches as well, such as that of Section 7. A general heuristic for statistics of torsion elements in class groups was proposed by Cohen and Lenstra [11]; their heuristic has inspired a great deal of interesting follow-up work, but for the most part the Cohen-Lenstra heuristics remain wide open.

3. Davenport-Heilbronn, Delone-Faddeev, and the Main Terms

In this section we discuss the proofs of the main terms in Theorems 1 and 2. To summarize, the idea is as follows: We count cubic *fields* by counting their *maximal orders*, and so we count all cubic orders and then sieve for maximality. We count cubic orders by counting cubic *rings* and then subtracting the contribution of the reducible rings, and these correspond to binary cubic *forms*. (The space of binary cubic forms is *prehomogeneous* in the sense described previously.) Thus at last we have a geometric lattice-point counting problem, which can be attacked using “brute force”. This interpretation in terms of lattice points also opens the door to the use of zeta functions.

We recommend the paper of Bhargava, Shankar, and Tsimerman [7] for the simplest self-contained account of the Davenport-Heilbronn theorems, with complete proofs.

We begin by defining cubic rings and cubic forms. A *cubic ring* is a commutative ring which is free of rank 3 as a \mathbb{Z} -module. The discriminant of a cubic ring is defined to be the determinant of the trace form $\langle x, y \rangle = \text{Tr}(xy)$, and the discriminant of the maximal order of a cubic field is equal to the discriminant of the field.

The lattice of *integral binary cubic forms* is defined by

$$V_{\mathbb{Z}} := \{au^3 + bu^2v + cvv^2 + dv^3 : a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{Z}\}, \quad (11)$$

and the *discriminant* of such a form is given by the usual formula

$$\text{Disc}(f) = b^2c^2 - 4ac^3 - 4b^3d - 27a^2d^2 + 18abcd. \quad (12)$$

There is a natural action of $\text{GL}_2(\mathbb{Z})$ (and also of $\text{SL}_2(\mathbb{Z})$) on $V_{\mathbb{Z}}$, given by

$$(\gamma \cdot f)(u, v) = \frac{1}{\det \gamma} f((u, v) \cdot \gamma). \quad (13)$$

We call a cubic form *f* *irreducible* if $f(u, v)$ is irreducible as a polynomial over \mathbb{Q} , and *nondegenerate* if $\text{Disc}(f) \neq 0$.

Cubic rings are related to cubic forms by the following correspondence of Delone and Faddeev, as further extended by Gan, Gross, and Savin [20]:

Theorem 5. ([16, 20]) *There is a natural, discriminant-preserving bijection between the set of $\mathrm{GL}_2(\mathbb{Z})$ -equivalence classes of integral binary cubic forms and the set of isomorphism classes of cubic rings. Furthermore, under this correspondence, irreducible cubic forms correspond to orders in cubic fields.*

Finally, if $x \in V_{\mathbb{Z}}$ is a cubic form corresponding to a cubic ring R , we have $\mathrm{Stab}_{\mathrm{GL}_2(\mathbb{Z})}(x) \simeq \mathrm{Aut}(R)$.

It is therefore necessary to exclude reducible and nonmaximal rings. The non-maximality condition is the more difficult of the two to handle, and for this Davenport and Heilbronn established the following criterion:

Proposition 6. ([15, 7]) Under the Delone-Faddeev correspondence, a cubic ring R is maximal if and only if its corresponding cubic form f belongs to the set $U_p \subset V_{\mathbb{Z}}$ for all p , defined by the following equivalent conditions:

- The ring R is not contained in any other cubic ring with index divisible by p .
- The cubic form f is not a multiple of p , and there is no $\mathrm{GL}_2(\mathbb{Z})$ -transformation of $f(u, v) = au^3 + bu^2v + cuv^2 + dv^3$ such that a is a multiple of p^2 and b is a multiple of p .

In particular, the condition U_p only depends on the coefficients of f modulo p^2 .

Therefore one can count cubic fields as follows. One obtains an asymptotic formula for the number of cubic rings of bounded discriminant by counting lattice points in fundamental domains for the action of $\mathrm{GL}_2(\mathbb{Z})$, bounded by the constraint $|\mathrm{Disc}(x)| < X$. The fundamental domains may be chosen so that almost all reducible rings correspond to forms with $a = 0$, and so these may be excluded from the count.

One then multiplies this asymptotic by the product of all the local densities of the sets U_p . This gives a heuristic argument for the main term in (1), and one incorporates a sieve to obtain a proof.

The main term of Theorem 2 may be proved similarly. By class field theory, there is a bijection between subgroups of $\mathrm{Cl}_3(\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{D}))$ of index 3, and cubic fields of discriminant D , which are precisely those not totally ramified at any prime. This ramification condition may also be detected by reducing cubic forms modulo p^2 , and thus may be incorporated into Proposition 6. The remainder of the proof is the same.

3.1. The Work of Belabas, Bhargava, and Pomerance

In [2], Belabas, Bhargava, and Pomerance (BBP) introduced improvements to Davenport and Heilbronn’s method, and obtained an error term of $O(X^{7/8+\epsilon})$ in (1) and (2). They began by observing that

$$N_3^{\pm}(X) = \sum_{q \geq 1} \mu(q) N^{\pm}(q, X), \tag{14}$$

where $N^\pm(q, X)$ counts the number of cubic orders of discriminant $0 < \pm D < X$ which are nonmaximal at every prime dividing q . This simple observation has proved to be quite useful! For large q , BBP prove that $N^\pm(q, X) \ll X3^{\omega(q)}/q^2$ using reasonably elementary methods. Therefore, one has

$$N_3^\pm(X) = \sum_{q \leq Q} \mu(q)N^\pm(q, X) + O(X/Q^{1-\epsilon}). \tag{15}$$

For small q , BBP estimate $N^\pm(q, X)$ with explicit error terms using geometric methods. These error terms are good enough to allow them to take the sum in (14) up to $Q = (X \log X)^{1/8}$, which yields a final error term of $O(X^{7/8+\epsilon})$.

In addition, their methods extend to counting S_4 -quartic fields where they obtain a main term of C_4X with error $\ll X^{23/24+\epsilon}$.

4. The Four Approaches

This, then, brings us to Theorems 1 and 2. Theorem 1 was conjectured in print by Roberts [32], and implicitly in the foundational work of Datskovsky and Wright [41, 13, 14]. Roberts gave substantial and convincing numerical evidence for his conjecture, as well as the heuristic argument described in Section 5.

The four approaches discussed in this paper are the following:

Shintani zeta functions (Taniguchi-T. [37, 38]). Taniguchi and the author further developed the theory of Shintani zeta functions, and proved Theorems 1 and 2 with error terms of $O(X^{7/9+\epsilon})$ and $O(X^{18/23+\epsilon})$, respectively. These proofs closely follow the heuristic arguments of Roberts and Datskovsky-Wright.

The Shintani zeta function approach is quite flexible, and [37] contains several generalizations of the main theorems. Perhaps the most interesting of these is a generalization to counting cubic field discriminants (or 3-torsion elements of class groups) in arithmetic progressions, where a certain “non-equidistribution” phenomenon arises. For example, when counting cubic field discriminants $\equiv a \pmod{7}$, the secondary term in Theorem 1 is different for every residue class $a \pmod{7}$.

A refined geometric approach (Bhargava, Shankar, and Tsimerman [7]). Bhargava, Shankar, and Tsimerman gave the first proof of Theorem 1, with an error term of $O(X^{13/16+\epsilon})$. Their proof follows Davenport and Heilbronn’s original work, counting lattice points via geometric arguments, with substantial simplifications and improvements.

Their proof of the secondary term is based on a “slicing” argument which we describe briefly in Section 6. Their treatment of the error terms introduces a certain correspondence for nonmaximal cubic rings; this correspondence has also proved useful in the context of Shintani zeta functions, and a combined approach ([8], in progress) has yielded an error term of $O(X^{2/3+\epsilon})$.

Equidistribution of Heegner points (Hough [24]). Hough obtained a statement closely related to Theorem 2. His scope is limited to counting 3-torsion elements in imaginary quadratic fields $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{D})$ with $D \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$; in this context, he proves a version of Theorem 2, but with an error term larger than $X^{5/6}$. In follow-up work (in preparation), he proves the secondary term for a *smoothed* variation of this sum.

Hough derives this result as a consequence of an equidistribution theorem for the Heegner points associated to the 3-part of class groups of imaginary quadratic fields; his proof of the Davenport-Heilbronn theorem appears as a bonus, and without reference to binary cubic forms. His techniques also apply to the k -parts of these class groups, for odd $k \geq 5$, where he obtains secondary terms (of order $X^{1/2+1/k}$). His error terms are currently larger than both the secondary and the main terms for $k \geq 5$, but this work sheds light on a notoriously difficult problem.

Trigonal curves and the Maroni invariant (Zhao [45]). Zhao enumerates cubic extensions of the rational function field $\mathbb{F}_q(t)$ using algebraic geometry. Such extensions are in bijection with isomorphism classes of smooth trigonal curves, that is, smooth 3-fold covers of \mathbb{P}^1 , and these may be counted by embedding them in certain surfaces F_k . He obtains a secondary term as a consequence of a bound for the integer k , called the Maroni invariant; for now his error terms are larger than this secondary term.

In all of these approaches, the secondary term is easier to see than it is to prove. In particular, each of these approaches yield the secondary term in a natural way, but it is not *a priori* evident that the error terms can be made smaller than $X^{5/6}$!

In what follows, we will describe, insofar as we can in a couple of pages, why each of these approaches naturally yields a secondary term. For the Shintani zeta function approach, we will say only a little about the error term, and for the other approaches we will say nothing. Indeed, we will use the notation $O(\dots)$ whenever the details are best left to the respective papers.

5. The Shintani Zeta Function Approach

Taniguchi and the author [37] proved Theorems 1 and 2 using the analytic theory of Shintani zeta functions. The *Shintani zeta functions* associated to the space of binary cubic forms are defined⁵ by the Dirichlet series

$$\xi^\pm(s) := \sum_{x \in \text{GL}_2(\mathbb{Z}) \backslash V_{\mathbb{Z}}^\pm} \frac{1}{|\text{Stab}_{\text{GL}_2(\mathbb{Z})}(x)|} |\text{Disc}(x)|^{-s} = \sum_{\pm \text{Disc}(R) > 0} \frac{1}{|\text{Aut}(R)|} |\text{Disc}(R)|^{-s}. \tag{16}$$

⁵The Shintani zeta functions are commonly defined in terms of $\text{SL}_2(\mathbb{Z})$ rather than $\text{GL}_2(\mathbb{Z})$, multiplying (16) by a factor of 2.

In the former sum, $V_{\mathbb{Z}}$ is the lattice defined in (11), the sum is over elements of positive or negative discriminant respectively, and $\text{Stab}(x)$ is the stabilizer of x in $\text{GL}_2(\mathbb{Z})$. The latter sum is over isomorphism classes of cubic rings. The equality of these two series follows from the Delone-Faddeev correspondence (Theorem 5).

This is an example of a zeta function associated to a prehomogeneous vector space. The definition of ‘prehomogeneous’ concerns the $\text{GL}_2(\mathbb{C})$ action on $V_{\mathbb{C}}$, but here the important (related) fact is that $\text{GL}_2(\mathbb{R})$ acts transitively on the positive- and negative-discriminant loci $V_{\mathbb{R}}^{\pm}$. Sato and Shintani [34] developed a general theory of zeta functions associated to prehomogeneous vector spaces, and for the space of binary cubic forms Shintani proved [35] that these zeta functions enjoy analytic continuation and an explicit functional equation. These zeta functions have poles at $s = 1$, as is common for zeta functions, and at $s = 5/6$, which is much more unusual.

Shintani’s work opens the door to the study of cubic fields using analytic number theory. In particular, by Perron’s formula and standard techniques we have

$$\sum_{\substack{x \in \text{GL}_2(\mathbb{Z}) \backslash V_{\mathbb{Z}} \\ \pm \text{Disc}(x) < X}} \frac{1}{|\text{Stab}(x)|} = \int_{2-i\infty}^{2+i\infty} \xi^{\pm}(s) \frac{X^s}{s} ds$$

$$= \text{Res}_{s=1} \xi^{\pm}(s) X + \frac{6}{5} \text{Res}_{s=5/6} \xi^{\pm}(s) X^{5/6} + O(X^{3/5+\epsilon}). \quad (17)$$

Although the left side is not the counting function of cubic fields, for the first time we see the $X^{5/6}$ secondary term. This, therefore, gives an explanation for the secondary terms in Theorems 1 and 2: because the Shintani zeta functions have secondary poles.⁶

To count cubic fields, the most important step is sieving for maximality. This is possible by work of Datskovsky and Wright [41, 13, 14], who gave Shintani’s work an adelic formulation along the lines of Tate’s thesis [39]. This allowed them to incorporate a variety of conditions into the definition of the Shintani zeta functions, including the Davenport-Heilbronn maximality conditions (given in Proposition 6).

A bogus proof of Roberts’ conjecture is as follows. For a set of primes \mathcal{P} , define the \mathcal{P} -maximal Shintani zeta function by the Dirichlet series (16), with the added condition that the only cubic forms counted are those in the set U_p for each $p \in \mathcal{P}$. Therefore, letting \mathcal{P} be the set of primes $< X$, it follows that

$$\sum'_{\pm \text{Disc}(x) < R} \frac{1}{|\text{Aut}(R)|} = \int_{2-i\infty}^{2+i\infty} \xi_{\mathcal{P}}^{\pm}(s) \frac{X^s}{s} ds$$

$$= \text{Res}_{s=1} \xi_{\mathcal{P}}^{\pm}(s) X + \frac{6}{5} \text{Res}_{s=5/6} \xi_{\mathcal{P}}^{\pm}(s) X^{5/6} + O(X^{3/5+\epsilon}), \quad (18)$$

⁶Of course, this begs the question of why the Shintani zeta functions have poles at $s = 5/6$. This can of course be explained by the various calculations in Shintani’s work, but for now a satisfying highbrow argument is unknown to the author.

where the sum is over all *maximal* cubic rings, corresponding to fields of degree ≤ 3 , with $\pm \text{Disc}(R) < X$. The quadratic fields (and \mathbb{Q}) can easily be counted and subtracted, but the error term in (18) depends on the particular zeta function $\xi_{\mathcal{P}}$, and therefore the implied constant depends on X (indeed, when standard techniques are used, exponentially so!).

However, this flawed argument enabled Datskovsky and Wright [14] to give a rigorous analytic proof of the Davenport-Heilbronn theorem. The key step⁷ is to use (18), but with \mathcal{P} equal to the set of all primes $< Y$, where Y tends to infinity very slowly with X . Given their adelic framework, their work yielded an asymptotic formula for the number of cubic extensions of any global field of characteristic not 2 or 3.

Moreover, Roberts [32] computed the limit of the secondary terms in (18) and found an excellent match with numerical data. This led him to conjecture that (18) (equivalently, (1)) was correct with some undetermined error term smaller than $X^{5/6}$.

He closed his paper with the following (paraphrased very slightly):

The pessimistic discussion in [14] suggests to us that the way may be difficult. However, one ingredient of a proof might be the functional equation of $\xi_{\mathcal{P}}^{\pm}(s)$ with respect to $s \rightarrow 1 - s$, studied in [41, 13]. Another ingredient might be [[34], Thm. 3], which concerns growth of arithmetic functions whose associated Dirichlet series satisfy such a functional equation.

This is actually a good summary of our proofs of Theorems 1 and 2! To get the ball rolling, we needed to incorporate the sieve used by Belabas, Bhargava, and Pomerance described in Section 3. In place of the \mathcal{P} -maximal zeta function we introduced the *q-nonmaximal zeta function*, which counts only cubic rings *not* maximal at each prime dividing q . This allowed us to count maximal cubic rings, and the irreducible such rings correspond to cubic fields.

Remark. As described at the end of Section 2, we count 3-torsion elements of class groups by a variation of this argument. Such elements correspond to cubic fields not totally ramified at any prime, and so we expand the definition of the *q-nonmaximal zeta function* to count cubic rings either nonmaximal or totally ramified at every prime dividing q .

The equation (18) holds for each *q-nonmaximal zeta function*, and the *q-dependence* of the error term can be bounded in terms of the exponential sum

$$\sum_{x \in V_{\mathbb{Z}/q^2\mathbb{Z}}} |\widehat{\Phi}_q(x)| := \sum_{x \in V_{\mathbb{Z}/q^2\mathbb{Z}}} \left| \frac{1}{q^8} \sum_{y \in V_{\mathbb{Z}/q^2\mathbb{Z}}} \Phi_q(y) \exp(2\pi i[x, y]/q^2) \right|, \quad (19)$$

⁷We have adapted their argument somewhat to our point of view. Datskovsky and Wright also need, as did Davenport and Heilbronn, the bound (15) for the number of cubic rings nonmaximal at any prime $> Y$.

where $\Phi_q(x)$ is the characteristic function of the Davenport-Heilbronn q -nonmaximality condition, and $[x, y] = x_4y_1 - \frac{1}{3}x_3y_2 + \frac{1}{3}x_2y_3 - x_1y_4$. Each inner sum appears naturally when we shift the contour in (18) to the left of $\Re(s) = 0$ and apply the functional equation. Trivially, the sum in (19) is bounded by q^8 ; this is enough to allow us to take $Q = X^{1/25}$ in (15) and obtain an error term of $X^{24/25+\epsilon}$ in the Davenport-Heilbronn theorems. We could improve this using the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality, but not below $X^{5/6}$.

In [37] we incorporated several improvements to lower the error terms in Theorems 1 and 2 to $O(X^{7/9+\epsilon})$ and $O(X^{18/23+\epsilon})$, respectively. Among these is a careful analysis of the sum in (19), carried out in [38]. For each x we obtained exact formulas for the inner sum in (19), proving that the outer sum is $\ll q^{1+\epsilon}$.

5.1. Non-Equidistribution in Arithmetic Progressions

The Shintani zeta function approach can also be used to study the distribution of cubic field discriminants in arithmetic progressions. To do this, one twists the Shintani zeta functions by Dirichlet characters, obtaining L -functions which are also proved to enjoy analytic continuation and a functional equation.

The details are complicated, so here we simply present representative numerical data. The tables below list the number of cubic fields K with $0 < \text{Disc}(K) < 2 \cdot 10^6$ and $\text{Disc}(K) \equiv a \pmod{m}$, for $m = 5$ and $m = 7$, and each residue class a .

Discriminant modulo 5	0	1	2	3	4
Actual count	21277	22887	22751	22748	22781
Theoretical result	21307	22757	22757	22757	22757
Difference	30	130	6	9	24

Discriminant modulo 7	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Actual count	15330	17229	14327	15323	17027	18058	15150
Theoretical result	15316	17209	14277	15316	17024	18063	15131
Difference	14	20	50	7	3	5	19

The data modulo 5 is essentially equidistributed, apart from the $a = 0$ column. (The relative deficit of cubic fields divisible by 5, or by any other modulus, can be explained by a careful reading of Davenport and Heilbronn’s original paper.) However, the data modulo 7 shows a striking lack of equidistribution.⁸

The theoretical results above come from a generalization of Theorem 1 to arithmetic progressions; the secondary term now involves a sum of residues of twisted Shintani zeta functions. These residues are evaluated in [38], and for characters χ for which $\chi^6 \neq 1$, the associated residue at $s = 5/6$ is zero. However, when $\chi^6 = 1$ this residue is often nonzero, and nonzero residues explain biases in arithmetic progressions such as the one seen above.

⁸The counting functions for cubic field discriminants $\equiv 0 \pmod{7}$ and $\equiv 3 \pmod{7}$ are not the same. The main term for $0 \pmod{7}$ is smaller than that for $3 \pmod{7}$, the secondary term is larger, and the equality in the second row of the table is a coincidence of roundoff error.

6. A Refined Geometric Approach

To give an overview of Bhargava, Shankar, and Tsimerman’s proof [7], we start with their treatment of the main term in Theorem 1. Later, we will describe how the secondary term appears in their work, but only in the context of irreducible cubic forms (corresponding to cubic orders).

The argument in [7] largely follows Davenport and Heilbronn’s original work. Fix a sign, and let V_{irr}^{\pm} denote the irreducible points $x \in V_{\mathbb{Z}}$ with $\pm \text{Disc}(x) > 0$. Write $n_+ = 6, n_- = 2$ for the order of the stabilizers of the action of $\text{GL}_2(\mathbb{R})$ on $V_{\mathbb{R}}^{\pm}$. The equality $n_+ = 3n_-$ is reflected in the fact that cubic fields of negative discriminant are three times as common as those of positive discriminant.

Write \mathcal{F} for a certain fundamental domain for $\text{GL}_2(\mathbb{Z}) \backslash \text{GL}_2(\mathbb{R})$ in $\text{GL}_2(\mathbb{R})$ (see (12) of [7]), originally constructed by Gauss. For any $v \in V^{\pm}$, consider the multiset $\mathcal{F}v$, where the multiplicity of an element $x \in V^{\pm}$ is equal to the number of $g \in \mathcal{F}$ for which $gv = x$. It is readily checked that each element $x \in G_{\mathbb{Z}} \backslash V_{\mathbb{Z}}^{\pm}$ is represented in this multiset $n_{\pm}/m(x)$ times, where $m(x)$ denotes the size of the stabilizer of x in $\text{GL}_2(\mathbb{Z})$. We conclude that

$$N(V^{\pm}; X) := \sum_{\substack{0 < \pm \text{Disc}(x) < X \\ x \text{ irred.}}} \frac{1}{|\text{Stab}(x)|} = \frac{1}{n_{\pm}} \#\{x \in \mathcal{F}v \cap V_{\text{irr}}^{\pm} : |\text{Disc}(x)| < X\}. \tag{20}$$

The reducible points can be handled without too much difficulty: The number of reducible integral binary cubic forms $au^3 + bu^2v + cuv^2 + dv^3$ in the multiset $\mathcal{R}_X(v) := \{w \in \mathcal{F}v : |\text{Disc}(w)| < X\}$, satisfying $a \neq 0$, is $\ll X^{3/4+\epsilon}$. Conversely, all cubic forms with $a = 0$ are reducible. This condition $a \neq 0$ meshes well with the geometric arguments that follow. In addition, the weight $\frac{1}{|\text{Stab}(x)|}$ occurring in (20) can be neglected, as there are $\ll X^{1/2}$ points x with $|\text{Disc}(x)| < X$ with nontrivial stabilizer.

The formula in (20) does not depend on v , and one innovation of [7] (previously used by Bhargava in [3]) is to average over many v . In particular, define $B := \{w = (a, b, c, d) \in V : 3a^2 + b^2 + c^2 + 3d^2 \leq 10, |\text{Disc}(w)| \geq 1\}$, and we have

$$N(V^{\pm}; X) = \frac{\int_{v \in B \cap V^{\pm}} \frac{1}{n_{\pm}} \#\{x \in \mathcal{F}v \cap V_{\text{irr}}^{\pm} : |\text{Disc}(x)| < X\} |\text{Disc}(v)|^{-1} dv}{\int_{v \in B \cap V^{\pm}} |\text{Disc}(v)|^{-1} dv}. \tag{21}$$

The authors describe this step as “thickening the cusp”. As $|\text{Disc}(v)|^{-1} dv$ is $\text{GL}_2(\mathbb{R})$ -invariant, we may rewrite this as

$$N(V^{\pm}; X) = \frac{1}{M^{\pm}} \int_{g \in \mathcal{F}} \#\{x \in V_{\text{irr}}^{\pm} \cap gB : |\text{Disc}(x)| < X\} dg, \tag{22}$$

where $M^{\pm} := \frac{n_{\pm}}{2\pi} \int_{v \in B \cap V^{\pm}} |\text{Disc}(v)|^{-1} dv$. This is rewritten as

$$N(V^{\pm}, X) = \frac{1}{M^{\pm}} \int_{g \in N'(a)A'\Lambda} \#\{x \in V_{\text{irr}}^{\pm} \cap B(n, t, \lambda, X)\} t^{-2} dnd^{\times} td^{\times} \lambda \tag{23}$$

using a standard decomposition of \mathcal{F} ((12) of [7]), where $B(n, t, \lambda, X)$ is the region $\{x \in gB : |\text{Disc}(x)| < X\}$. A proposition of Davenport establishes that in this situation, the count of lattice points above is well approximated by the volume of $B(n, t, \lambda, X)$, provided that t is not too large. Conversely, when t is large all the lattice points are in the cusp $a = 0$, and hence reducible and not counted. Thus, the above is reduced to

$$N(V^\pm, X) = \frac{1}{M^\pm} \int_{\substack{g \in N'(a)A'\Lambda \\ t < C^{1/3}\lambda^{1/3}}} \text{Vol}(B(n, t, \lambda, X))t^{-2}dnd^\times td^\times \lambda + O(\dots). \tag{24}$$

The condition on t is now removed, subject to an error term, and this integral is equal to

$$N(V^\pm, X) = \frac{1}{2\pi M^\pm} \int_{v \in B \cap V^\pm} \text{Vol}(\mathcal{R}_X(v))|\text{Disc}(v)|^{-1}dv + O(\dots). \tag{25}$$

This volume does not in fact depend on v , so that we have (excluding error terms)

$$N(V^\pm, X) = \frac{1}{n_\pm} \text{Vol}(\mathcal{R}_X(v)) = \frac{\pi^2}{12n_\pm} X. \tag{26}$$

6.1. Origin of the Secondary Term

We now explain how Bhargava, Shankar, and Tsimerman refine these calculations to obtain a secondary term. Our brief explanation will necessarily be somewhat vague, which should encourage the reader to read [7]. We focus on their count of irreducible binary cubic forms; as in [2, 37], they also incorporate a sieve to count cubic fields.

They begin by incorporating several tweaks to (23). For technical reasons, they count discriminants in dyadic intervals $[X/2, X]$. In addition, they introduce a smooth function $\Psi_0(t)$ on $\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$, such that $\Psi_0(t) = 0$ for $t \leq 2$ and $\Psi_0(t) = 1$ for $t \geq 3$. They thus rewrite (23) (restricted to a dyadic interval $[X/2, X]$) as

$$N(V^\pm, [X/2, X]) = \frac{1}{M^\pm} \int_{g \in N'(a)A'\Lambda} \left(\Psi_0\left(\frac{t\kappa}{\lambda^{1/3}}\right) + \Psi\left(\frac{t\kappa}{\lambda^{1/3}}\right) \right) \times \#\{x \in V_{\text{irr}}^\pm \cap B(n, t, \lambda, [X/2, X])\}t^{-2}dnd^\times td^\times \lambda, \tag{27}$$

where $\Psi := 1 - \Psi_0$, and κ is a parameter to be chosen later (to minimize error terms). The decomposition $\Psi + \Psi_0 = 1$ splits this integral into two, and we restrict our attention to the Ψ_0 part, which yields the secondary term.

They now “slice” the count of binary cubic forms by the first coordinate. In particular, for $a \in \mathbb{Z}$, let $B_a(n, t, \lambda, [X/2, X])$ denote the set of binary cubic forms in $B_a(n, t, \lambda, [X/2, X])$ whose u^3 coefficient is equal to a . Then, we have

$$\#\{x \in V_{\text{irr}}^\pm \cap B(n, t, \lambda, [X/2, X])\} = \sum_{\substack{a \in \mathbb{Z} \\ a \neq 0}} \#\{x \in V_{\text{irr}}^\pm \cap B_a(n, t, \lambda, [X/2, X])\}. \tag{28}$$

Skipping ahead in their work, the Ψ_0 -contribution to (27) is equal to

$$\frac{2}{3M^\pm} \sum_{a=1}^\infty \int_{\lambda=(\sqrt{3/2})^3/C}^{X^{1/4}} \int_{u>0} \Phi_0\left(\frac{u^{1/3}\kappa}{a^{1/3}}\right) \frac{\lambda^{10/3}u^{1/3}}{a^{1/3}} \times \text{Vol}(B_u([X/(2\lambda^4), X/\lambda^4])) d^\times u d^\times \lambda + O(\dots), \tag{29}$$

where $B_a([Y/2, Y])$ denotes the set of cubic forms in B with first coordinate a and discriminant in $[Y/2, Y]$. By Mellin inversion, we have

$$\sum_{a=1}^\infty a^{-1/3} \Phi_0\left(\frac{u^{1/3}\kappa}{a^{1/3}}\right) = \zeta(1/3) + 3\tilde{\Phi}_0(-2)(\kappa^3u)^{2/3} + O(\dots), \tag{30}$$

and it is this (negative) $\zeta(1/3)$ which contributes the secondary term. In contrast, the second term of (30) (which “looks larger”, especially in light of the eventual choice $\kappa = X^{1/12}$) is reincorporated into (29) and then combined with the Ψ term of (27) to obtain the main term in (26). When the $\zeta(1/3)$ term is plugged into (29), the resulting integral can be evaluated without undue difficulty, and it has order $X^{5/6}$.

Remark. As Shankar has explained to the author, a more geometric argument can also be given, which does not rely on the analytic continuation of the Riemann zeta function. However, it is unclear whether the resulting error term would be smaller than $X^{5/6}$ when combined with the sieve.

6.2. A Correspondence for Cubic Forms

To count cubic fields one must sieve for maximality, using the Davenport-Heilbronn conditions of Proposition 6. These could be treated in a naive manner, but the authors improve their error terms by introducing a useful correspondence for non-maximal cubic forms.⁹

We introduce some notation. Let $N^\pm(V_{\mathbb{Z}}; X)$ count all cubic forms v with $0 < \pm \text{Disc}(v) < X$. For a prime p , let $N^\pm(U_p^c; X)$ count those cubic forms which are nonmaximal at p , i.e., which do not lie in the set U_p defined in Proposition 6. (In referring to cubic forms as “nonmaximal” we are implicitly appealing to the Delone-Faddeev correspondence.) Finally, for any $\alpha \in \mathbb{P}^1(\mathbb{Z}/p\mathbb{Z})$, let $N^\pm(V_{p,\alpha}; X)$ count those cubic forms v such that the reduction of v modulo p has α as a root.

With this notation, we have the following correspondence:

Proposition 7. ([7]) We have the identity

$$N^\pm(U_p^c; X) = \sum_{\alpha \in \mathbb{P}^1(\mathbb{F}_p)} N^\pm(V_{p,\alpha}; X/p^2) - \sum_{\alpha \in \mathbb{P}^1(\mathbb{F}_p)} N^\pm(V_{p,\alpha}; X/p^4) + N^\pm(V_{\mathbb{Z}}; X/p^4). \tag{31}$$

⁹As Shankar explained to me, in the case of cubic fields it is this correspondence which allows them to cross the $X^{5/6}$ barrier.

This identity generalizes in a straightforward way from prime p to squarefree q , where we count cubic forms not in U_p for any $p|q$. The identity amounts to a combinatorial argument, enumerating ways in which a nonmaximal cubic ring is contained in a larger ring (with smaller discriminant), and then counting these larger rings.

This identity is crucial in [7], and it can also be translated into an identity for the q -nonmaximal Shintani zeta function! In work in progress by Bhargava, Taniguchi, and the author [8] we are developing this combined approach. We have proved an error term of $O(X^{2/3+\epsilon})$ in Theorem 1 as well as a secondary term for relative cubic extensions of quadratic base fields, and we are currently working on further extensions and generalizations.

7. Equidistribution of Heegner Points

Remarkably, Hough [24] demonstrated that the Delone-Faddeev correspondence is not the only path to the Davenport-Heilbronn theorem. Hough studied the distribution of Heegner points associated to 3-torsion elements of ideal class groups of quadratic fields, and he obtained a result related to Theorem 2 as a consequence.

For simplicity, Hough worked only with imaginary discriminants $D \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$; note that any such discriminant is not fundamental, and the discriminant of the field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{D})$ is $4D$.¹⁰ He proves that

$$\sum_{\substack{0 < D < X \\ D \equiv 2 \pmod{4}}} \#\text{Cl}_3(-D) = \frac{4}{\pi^2} X + O(X^{19/20+\epsilon}), \tag{32}$$

and for compactly supported, infinitely differentiable test functions ϕ , he proves that

$$\sum_{\substack{0 < D \\ D \equiv 2 \pmod{4}}} \#\text{Cl}_3(-D)\phi(D/X) = \frac{4}{\pi^2} \widehat{\phi}(1)X + O(X^{7/8+\epsilon}). \tag{33}$$

The correct secondary term of order $X^{5/6}$ appears in both formulas, in spite of the larger error terms, and in follow-up work (in progress) he obtains an error less than $X^{5/6}$ in (33), thereby obtaining a proof of a related secondary term.

Hough’s work has very different prospects for generalization from the approaches described previously. In particular, his approach can be used to study k -torsion in class groups for odd $k > 3$, and he makes the following conjecture:

¹⁰It seems that the restrictions that $D \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$ and $-D < 0$ could both be lifted with some effort. The restriction on the sign is the more serious of the two, as elements of class groups of $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{D})$ for positive D correspond to closed geodesics rather than Heegner points. However, Duke’s result holds for either sign, so in [24] Hough expresses optimism that the positive discriminant case of Theorem 2 could be handled as well.

Conjecture 8. (Hough [24]) For good test functions ϕ and odd $k \geq 3$, we have

$$\sum_{\substack{0 < D \\ D \equiv 2 \pmod{4}}} \#\text{Cl}_k(-D)\phi(D/X) = \frac{4}{\pi^2}\widehat{\phi}(1)X + C_{1,k}\widehat{\phi}\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{k}\right)X^{1/2+1/k} + o(X^{1/2+1/k}), \tag{34}$$

where

$$C_{1,k} := \frac{1}{6k} \frac{\zeta(1 - \frac{2}{k})}{\zeta(2)} \frac{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2})\Gamma(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{k})}{\Gamma(1 - \frac{1}{k})} \left(1 - 2^{1/k} + 2^{1-1/k}\right) \times \prod_{p>2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{p+1} \left(p^{-1/k} - p^{-1+2/k} - p^{-1+1/k} - p^{-1}\right)\right). \tag{35}$$

Indeed he “proves” his conjecture, but with error terms larger than X . Even a proof of the main term for the single case $k = 5$ would be a major achievement. Indeed, the average size of $\text{Cl}_p(-D)$ was conjectured by Cohen and Lenstra [11] to be 2 for each prime $p \geq 3$, and Cohen and Lenstra further conjectured that the p -part of $\text{Cl}_p(-D)$ is isomorphic to a fixed p -group H with probability proportional to $\frac{1}{|\text{Aut}(H)|}$. No case of these conjectures is currently known for any $p \geq 5$, and essentially nothing is known for $p = 3$ beyond Theorem 2.

7.1. Heegner Points and Equidistribution

Hough’s main result concerns the equidistribution of Heegner points associated to the 3-part of the class group. We recall the relevant background. If $\mathfrak{a} = [x_1, x_2]$ is an ideal of an imaginary quadratic field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-D})$, where by reordering if necessary we have $x_1/x_2 \in \mathbb{H} := \{z \in \mathbb{C} : \Im(z) > 0\}$, we call x_1/x_2 the *Heegner point* $z_{\mathfrak{a}}$ associated to the ideal \mathfrak{a} . A change of basis for \mathfrak{a} corresponds to a linear fractional transformation $z_{\mathfrak{a}} \rightarrow \frac{az_{\mathfrak{a}}+b}{cz_{\mathfrak{a}}+d}$ with $ad - bc = 1$, and therefore the Heegner point $z_{\mathfrak{a}}$ is well-defined in the quotient $\text{SL}_2(\mathbb{Z})\backslash\mathbb{H}$. One checks that $z_{\mathfrak{a}} = z_{\alpha\mathfrak{a}}$ for any $\alpha \in \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-D})$, and hence $z_{\mathfrak{a}}$ depends only on the class of \mathfrak{a} in $\text{Cl}(\sqrt{-D})$. One similarly checks that $z_{\mathfrak{a}} \neq z_{\mathfrak{b}}$ if \mathfrak{a} and \mathfrak{b} are inequivalent in $\text{Cl}(\sqrt{-D})$.

Therefore, there are $h(-D)$ Heegner points associated to $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-D})$ in $\text{SL}_2(\mathbb{Z})\backslash\mathbb{H}$, and in [17] Duke proves that they equidistribute with respect to the hyperbolic measure $\frac{dx dy}{y^2}$ as $D \rightarrow \infty$. Hough proves the same for the Heegner points associated to the 3-part of the ideal class group:

Theorem 9. (Hough [24]) *Let B be a bounded Borel measurable subset of \mathbb{H} having boundary of measure zero. Then as $D \rightarrow \infty$,*

$$\sum_{\substack{0 > -D > -X \\ d \equiv 2 \pmod{4} \\ \text{squarefree}}} \#\{\mathfrak{a} \text{ primitive, nonprincipal} : [\mathfrak{a}] \in \text{Cl}_3(\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-D})), z_{\mathfrak{a}} \in B\} \sim \frac{6X}{\pi^3} \text{vol}(B). \tag{36}$$

Here we take $B \subseteq \mathbb{H}$ rather than $B \subseteq \mathrm{SL}_2(\mathbb{Z}) \backslash \mathbb{H}$, so that each Heegner point is counted once for each representative of its $\mathrm{SL}_2(\mathbb{Z})$ orbit in B . (We recall that a *primitive* ideal is one without any rational integer divisors other than 1.)

Straightaway one can see that this is an equidistribution statement. But it also implies the Davenport-Heilbronn theorem! Taking B to be the standard (or any other) fundamental domain for the action of $\mathrm{SL}_2(\mathbb{Z})$ on \mathbb{H} , one counts each Heegner point (and thus each nontrivial element of $\mathrm{Cl}_3(\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-D}))$) exactly once. The Davenport-Heilbronn theorem follows from the classical computation $\mathrm{vol}(B) = \frac{3}{\pi}$.

We will follow Hough’s approach sufficiently far as to see the secondary term. His work begins with the following parameterization of ideals (and therefore Heegner points), essentially due to Soundararajan [36].

Proposition 10. [24, 36] Let $D \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$ be squarefree and let $k \geq 3$ be odd. The set

$$\{(l, m, n, t) \in (\mathbb{Z}^+)^4 : lm^k = l^2n^2 + t^2D, l|D, (m, ntD) = 1\} \tag{37}$$

is in bijection with primitive ideal pairs $(\mathfrak{a}, \bar{\mathfrak{a}})$ with $\mathfrak{a} \neq 1$ and \mathfrak{a}^k principal in $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-D})$. Explicitly, the ideal \mathfrak{a} is given as a \mathbb{Z} -module by

$$\mathfrak{a} = [lm, lnt^{-1} + \sqrt{-D}]$$

where $\mathbb{N}\mathfrak{a} = lm$ and t^{-1} is the inverse of t modulo m .

The proof is relatively straightforward. For example, if \mathfrak{a}^k is principal and coprime to D , then $\mathfrak{a}^k = (n + t\sqrt{-D})$ and taking norms yields $(\mathbb{N}\mathfrak{a})^k = n^2 + t^2D$, a solution to (37). Ideals \mathfrak{a} not coprime to D yield solutions to (37) with $l > 1$.

As one of the two main steps in his proof, Hough now applies this parameterization to count Heegner points in the region

$$R_Y := \left\{ z \in \mathbb{H} : -\frac{1}{2} < \Re(z) < \frac{1}{2}, \Im(z) > \frac{1}{Y} \right\}. \tag{38}$$

This establishes the vertical distribution of Heegner points, and he separately establishes that they are equidistributed horizontally. He proves that the number of Heegner points in R_Y is equal to

$$\frac{6}{\pi^3} YX + C_{5/6} X^{5/6} + O(\dots), \tag{39}$$

for a fairly complicated error term depending on both X and Y . The secondary term appears here for the following reason: By the parameterization above, we may write an ideal \mathfrak{a} as $[lm, lnt^{-1} + \sqrt{-D}]$. We have $lm^3 = l^2n^2 + t^2D$, so that $lm \geq D^{1/3}$, implying that the Heegner point $z_{\mathfrak{a}}$ has imaginary part $\frac{\sqrt{D}}{lm} \leq D^{1/6} \leq X^{1/6}$. In other words, the Heegner points equidistribute as $X \rightarrow \infty$, but for fixed X they do not appear high in the cusp.

The hyperbolic volume of the subset of R_Y with $\Im(z) > X^{1/6}$ is equal to

$$\int_{x=-1/2}^{1/2} \int_{y=X^{1/6}}^{\infty} \frac{dx dy}{y^2} = X^{-1/6}. \tag{40}$$

Accounting (much more carefully than done here!) for the fact that this subset contains no Heegner points yields the negative secondary term in (39), and an analogous argument explains the second term in (34).

Remark. Hough’s methods also extend to arithmetic progressions, where he finds the same lack of equidistribution observed at the end of Section 5; some results along these lines are in preparation.

8. Hirzebruch Surfaces and the Maroni Invariant

Zhao’s work [45] is still in preparation, so we offer only a very brief overview here. Using algebraic geometry, Zhao estimates the number of cubic extensions of the rational function field $\mathbb{F}_q(t)$.

Fix a finite field \mathbb{F}_q of characteristic not equal to 2 or 3, and let $S(2N)$ be the number of isomorphism classes of cubic extensions $K/\mathbb{F}_q(t)$ of degree 3, such that $|\text{Disc}(F)| = q^{2N}$. In [14], Datskovsky and Wright proved that

$$S(2N) = 2 \frac{\text{Res}_{s=1} \zeta_{\mathbb{F}_q(t)}(1)}{\zeta_{\mathbb{F}_q(t)}(3)} q^{2N} + o(q^{2N}), \tag{41}$$

where $\zeta_{\mathbb{F}_q(t)}(s)$ is the Dedekind zeta function of $\mathbb{F}_q(t)$, or equivalently the zeta function of the algebraic curve $\mathbb{P}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^1$.

Datskovsky and Wright’s proof uses the adelic Shintani zeta function; in [45] Zhao obtains another proof of (41) using algebraic geometry. A *trigonal curve* is a 3-fold cover of \mathbb{P}^1 , and there is a bijection between isomorphism classes of smooth trigonal curves and cubic rational function fields. Already this perspective is enlightening; for example, the Riemann-Hurwitz formula implies that the discriminant has even degree, explaining why (41) is an equation for $S(2N)$ and not $S(N)$.

The problem, then, is to count smooth trigonal curves. These may be counted by embedding the curves into *Hirzebruch surfaces* F_k ; for each trigonal curve C there is a unique nonnegative integer k , called the *Maroni invariant* of C , such that C embeds into $F_k := \mathbb{P}_{\mathbb{P}^1}(\mathcal{O} \oplus \mathcal{O}(-k))$.

Zhao now counts curves on each surface F_k and sieves for smoothness, using a sieve method related to one developed by Poonen [31]. However, the main technique is different and new. The main term in (41) comes from estimating the number of trigonal curves C with each Maroni invariant k , and then summing the results over all integers k . However, the Maroni invariant of a smooth trigonal curve C is at most $N/3$, provided that the field corresponding to C has absolute discriminant q^{2N} . Limiting our sum to $k \leq N/3$ naturally introduces a secondary term of order $q^{5N/3}$ into (41).

Zhao's method, like all other methods described in this paper, comes with error terms; at present he has obtained an error term of $O(N^2 q^{5N/3})$ in (41), narrowly missing a proof of the secondary term. He has some optimism that this error term can be reduced below $q^{5N/3}$, and also that some of his methods may be adapted to say something interesting in the number field case.

9. Conclusion

Cubic fields have seen a great deal of recent study recently, and we recommend the papers of Cohen-Morra [12] and Martin-Pollack [26] (among others) for recent studies of cubic fields from other perspectives.

Many interesting open questions remain in the subject. For example, what is the "correct" error term in the Davenport-Heilbronn theorems? Even if we cannot prove it, it would still be interesting to determine the expected order of magnitude. To get the best error terms it seems that we should count fields K of degree *at most* 3, each weighted by $\frac{1}{|\text{Aut}(K)|}$. This is suggested both by numerical data and also by considering the space of binary cubic forms, where reducible maximal forms correspond to quadratic fields or to \mathbb{Q} . (Note that this heuristic does not generalize directly to higher degree fields.) The data in [32] suggests that the true error may be smaller than $X^{1/2}$, and a comparison with the divisor problem suggests that the error might be on the order of $X^{3/8}$. Nevertheless, the comparison with the divisor problem is not exact, and the numerical data is inconclusive.

Perhaps the most compelling open question concerns quartic and quintic fields. Asymptotic formulas were proved by Bhargava [3, 6]; should these formulas have secondary terms? It is generally believed that they should; however, so far we lack even a good conjecture. The zeta function approach seems likely to work, and Yukie [44] has made some progress in this direction; the geometric approach seems likely to work as well. However, for now the difficulties with either approach appear rather severe.

Another open question concerns the *multiplicity* of cubic fields. It is believed that there should be $\ll n^\epsilon$ cubic fields of discriminant $\pm n$, but the best bound known is $O(n^{1/3+\epsilon})$, due to Ellenberg and Venkatesh [19]. Nontrivial bounds were also obtained by Helfgott and Venkatesh [22] and Pierce [30], using a variety of methods. Any of the methods described in the present paper could potentially yield improvements, but none of them have succeeded to date. (The present author has attempted improvements by means of Shintani zeta functions, which have led to a number of instructive and interesting failures.)

Finally, this paper raises the question of whether unexpected connections might be found between the four perspectives presented here, and some promising preliminary results have been obtained in this direction. We anticipate that this and related questions will be addressed in the near future.

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